

Survey on Students' Use and Views on Generative AI in Computing Education

Excited, Skeptical, or Worried? A Multi-Institutional Study of Student Views on Generative AI in Computing Education

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Q2 How do you describe yourself?

- Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary / third gender
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe: _____
-

Q40 I am enrolled in

- High school
 - College (HBO / University of Applied Science)
 - University
-

Q5 What type of education are you following?

- senior general secondary education (HAVO)
 - pre university education (VWO/Gymnasium)
-

Q42 What year are you in?

- 4
 - 5
-

Q43 What year are you in?

- 4
 - 5
 - 6
-

Q41 What is your level of studies?

- Bachelor student
 - Master student
-

Q4 What is your enrolment type?

- Domestic student (from the Netherlands)
 - International student
-

Q44 What year are you in?

- 1
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5+
-

Q6 Are you the first person in your family to study at a university?

- Yes
 - No
 - Prefer not to say/Do not know
-

Q8 What is the name of your study program?

Q7 What is the name of your school/university?

Q9 Overall, what is the average grade you have gotten so far?

- Bellow 6
 - Around 6
 - Around 7
 - 8 or higher
 - Prefer not to say/Do not know
-

Q10 Have you done programming outside of your school/university?

- Yes, as a job
 - Yes, as a hobby
 - No
-

Q14 Please estimate, on a scale from 1 to 5, your proficiency in programming

Not proficient at all Slightly proficient Moderately proficient Proficient Very proficient

1 2 3 4 5

Q15 Please estimate, on the scale from 1 to 5, how important you think programming will be for your future career

Not at all important Slightly important Moderately important Very important Extremely important

1 2 3 4 5

Importance of programming for future career

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: GenAI Use

Q16 For each of these tasks, indicate how often you use Generative AI (GenAI) tools such as ChatGPT, Copilot, or Bard

	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Less often	Never
Working with text (e.g., writing emails, reports, summaries).	<input type="radio"/>				
Generating images.	<input type="radio"/>				
Generating code (e.g., the solution to a programming problem, or part of it).	<input type="radio"/>				
Finding and fixing errors in my code.	<input type="radio"/>				
Getting feedback on my code (reviewing).	<input type="radio"/>				
Learning about topics and concepts.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q18 Rate your level of agreement with the following statements

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Using GenAI tools frequently to generate code hinders my ability to learn programming.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am concerned that I will become overly reliant on GenAI tools.	<input type="radio"/>				
GenAI tools can provide guidance for coursework as effectively as human teachers.	<input type="radio"/>				

End of Block: GenAI Use

Start of Block: Policies and ethics

Q19 The policies of my school/university are clear regarding what is allowed and not allowed regarding the use of Generative AI (GenAI) tools.

- Strongly disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Neutral
- Somewhat agree
- Strongly agree

Q20 What is the general policy of your school/university on using GenAI tools in your studies?

- Not allowed
- Allowed
- It depends. Please explain:

- I don't know

Q21 How many students at your school/university are using GenAI tools in ways that teachers would not approve of?

- Almost everyone
- Many
- Some
- Almost no one

Q22 If a course does not have a policy regarding the use of GenAI tools, which of the following actions do you consider **ethical** (something that is fair or that you would not feel guilty about)? Select all that apply.

- Auto-generating a solution for the entire assignment (or a significant portion) and submitting it without understanding it.
 - Auto-generating a solution for the entire assignment (or a significant portion) and submitting it even after fully understanding it.
 - Auto-generating solutions for small parts of the assignment.
 - Using GenAI tools to “explain” step-by-step how to solve a problem.
 - Providing your code to GenAI tools and asking them to help fix a bug.
 - Asking GenAI tools to comment, tidy, and improve the style of your code.
 - Writing the solution in a programming language other than the course’s and asking GenAI tools to translate it.
-

Q23 Have you used GenAI to help you with part or all of an assignment when you were not supposed to?

- Never
 - Sometimes
 - Most of the time
 - Always
-

Q24 Should the use of GenAI for courses/exams be allowed, and why or why not?

End of Block: Policies and ethics

Start of Block: Attitudes

Q25 I trust what Generative AI (GenAI) generates (i.e., that it is accurate, reliable, appropriate)

- Strongly disagree
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
-

Q26 I change or edit what GenAI produces to suit my needs:

- Never
 - Sometimes
 - Most of the time
 - Always
-

Q27 Rate your level of agreement with each of these statements

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am optimistic about GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				
I am skeptical about GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				
I am worried about GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				
I am excited by GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				
I am stressed by GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				
I am grateful for GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				
I am frightened of GenAI	<input type="radio"/>				

Q28 Have your views on this topic changed over time? If yes, please explain how they have changed.

End of Block: Attitudes

Start of Block: Programming courses

Q31 Think about a recent course in which you did programming or programming-related tasks to answer the following questions

Q32 What is the topic of the course?

Q33 What is the role of programming in this course?

- The goal of the course is to learn programming.
 - Programming is necessary, but it is not the main focus.
 - Programming is optional.
-

Q47 Think about the Informatica-course/module when answering the following questions

Q34 What is your teacher's attitude towards using Generative AI (GenAI) tools?

- Mostly positive
 - Neutral or mixed
 - Mostly negative
 - I do not know
-

Q35 Can you elaborate on when you believe GenAI should be allowed or disallowed in this course?

Q36 In this course, I **want** to use GenAI because it

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Makes things easier or faster	<input type="radio"/>				
Improves the quality of my work	<input type="radio"/>				
Helps me do things I could not do otherwise	<input type="radio"/>				
Improves my grades	<input type="radio"/>				
Helps me feel more confident	<input type="radio"/>				

Q37 In this course, I **don't want** to use GenAI because

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am worried about breaking my university's rules	<input type="radio"/>				
It can be inaccurate or make things up	<input type="radio"/>				
I do not know how to use it confidently	<input type="radio"/>				
I want to do it myself	<input type="radio"/>				
I have privacy or ethical concerns	<input type="radio"/>				

Q38 If you have used GenAI tools in this course for coding tasks (e.g., generating/debugging/reviewing code), please describe how:

Q39 Rate your agreement with the following statements

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
GenAI tools have played a significant role in my learning process during this course.	<input type="radio"/>				
GenAI tools have accelerated my learning process in this course.	<input type="radio"/>				
Without GenAI, I believe I would have learned the same amount in this course.	<input type="radio"/>				

Q17 When you had a question regarding the material you were studying in this course or got stuck on a problem, in what order did you do the following? (Top = first thing you did, Bottom = last thing you did)

- _____ Ask using GenAI tools.
- _____ Ask on the course discussion forum/website.
- _____ Search online (e.g., Google).
- _____ Ask a friend or classmate.
- _____ Ask on online forums like StackOverflow.
- _____ Ask the instructor/TA

Q40 How do you feel the use of GenAI tools has affected your learning process in this course? Please describe any specific instances where AI tools have notably enhanced or hindered your learning.

End of Block: Programming courses

Start of Block: High school - future

Q45 Have you considered to study Computer Science (or a related study)?

- Yes, I still consider this
 - Yes, but not anymore
 - No
 - I don't know yet
-

Q46 Has the rise of GenAI changed this decision?

- Yes, in a positive way, I consider it more
- Yes, in a negative way, I consider it less
- No

End of Block: High school - future
